

AUTOMATED AUDIO CAPTIONING WITH LIMITED TRAINING DATA

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ABSTRACT

This task can be stated as an automated generation textual content description from the raw audio file. We propose a method for the automated audio captioning task with following conditions: limited training data amount, pre-trained models are not allowed. We examine the impact of augmentations (Input and Manifold MixUp, Reverb, Pitch, Over-drive, Speed) and attention on method performance. Our method based on modified encoder-decoder architecture. The encoder consists of three bidirectional gated recurrent units (GRU). The decoder includes one gated recurrent unit (GRU), attention mechanism and one fully-connected layer for classification. The encoder input is log-Mel Spectrogram features for every part of audio file segmented by Hann window of 1024 samples with a 50% overlap. The decoder output is a matrix with probabilities of words for each position in a sentence. We used BLEU₁, BLEU₂, BLEU₃, BLEU₄, ROUGE_L, METEOR, CIDEr, SPICE, SPIDEr metrics to compare methods.

Index Terms— Audio Captioning, Recurrent Neural Networks, Natural Language Generation, Augmentations, MixUp, Attention

1. INTRODUCTION

The automated audio captioning (AAC) problem can be stated as an annotation (textual description generation) of an audio track via an automated system (for example, neural networks). This task is essential because the audio classification approach is unable to explain inner relationships in audio. Audio captioning methods can model concepts, physical properties of objects and environment, and high-level knowledge (ex. "a cat meowed two times"). Also, audio captioning is more challenging than classification because it consists of two main tasks:

- audio processing,
- text generation.

There were a few papers before about audio captioning - [1], [2], and [3].

At first glance, the audio captioning task seems like image captioning, but there are some significant differences. Humans can easily annotate pictures, since every object on the image has a specific shape, color, size, etc. Most people more familiar with a visual representation than with an audio representation. For example, if we

consider Mel Spectrogram audio representation, we can notice the following differences between common images [4]:

1. Sound is "transparent" - highly likely one pixel of an image assumed to belong to a single object. In spectrograms it is not true.
2. The axes of spectrograms do not carry the same meaning, but in pictures x and y have the same meaning.
3. The spectral properties of sound are non-local. It means that neighboring pixels can't be assumed to belong to the same object as in pictures.

Results of an automated audio captioning algorithm can be used in different spheres: for hearing-impaired people, in manufacture (for more accurate description of emergencies), video analysis (we can describe video more explicitly with detailed information about the audio track).

Section 2 describes the dataset for training and evaluation, Section 3 tells about the proposed method (preprocessing, augmentations, neural network architectures, post-processing). The evaluation procedure, experiments, results are presented in Section 4. The conclusion and future work are described and discussed in Section 5.

2. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The task uses the freely available Clotho dataset [5]. It consists of audio samples of 15 to 30 seconds duration, and each audio sample has five captions of 8 to 20 words long.

There are a total of 4981 audio samples with 24 905 captions.

Clotho has 4365 unique words and is divided into three splits: development (60%), evaluation (20%), and testing (20%). All words appear proportionally between splits.

Words that cannot be divided using the above scheme of 60-20-20 appear at least one time in the development split and at least one time to one of the other two splits.

2.1. Audio samples information

Clotho audio data are extracted from an initial set of 12 000 audio files collected from Freesound [6]. The 12k audio files have durations ranging from 10s to 300s, no spelling errors, good quality (44.1kHz and 16-bit), and no tags on Freesound indicating sound

effects, music, or speech. Before extraction, all 12k files were normalized, and the leading and trailing silences were trimmed.

2.2. Captions information

The captions were gathered by employing the crowdsourcing platform Amazon Mechanical Turk and a three-step framework. The three steps are:

1. audio description;
2. description editing;
3. description scoring.

For detailed description see [7].

3. PROPOSED METHOD

3.1. Dataset preprocessing

Our method takes as an input raw, mono audio data with 44.1 kHz sampling frequency and 16 bits sample width and extracts log-Mel Spectrogram features for every part of audio file segmented by Hann window [8] of 1024 sample with 50% overlap. For each resulting part, we obtain $N_{\text{feats}} = 128$ features.

Captions preprocessing was taken from DCASE2020 Baseline code [9], which takes as an input CSV file with names of audio files in the first column and five captions per each audio file in the following five columns. Baseline code encodes caption with the Bag of Words model. Each sentence starts from "start of sentence" token (<SOS>) and ends by "end of sentence" token (<EOS>).

3.2. Data augmentation

Augmentations are essential in our work, because we have a limited amount of data.

• Input MixUp

First of all, we used **Input MixUp**, which was introduced in [10], with some differences in target mixing.

1. Audio tracks mixing.

The key idea is to mix random input audio files. For example, suppose we have in our train dataset audio x_i and audio x_j . The resulted audio after Input MixUp application will be:

$$x = \lambda x_i + (1 - \lambda)x_j, \text{ where } \lambda \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \alpha), \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = 16$

2. Captions mixing.

Suppose we have y_i and y_j captions corresponding to x_i and x_j , y_i has length l_i and $y_j - l_j$. There are several ways to implement captions mixing:

- Simple concatenation ($[y_i, y_j]$ or $[y_j, y_i]$)
- For definiteness, we assume $l_i > l_j$. We suppose y_i^k - k -th word in y_i . After concatenation we will get $[y_i^1, y_j^1, y_i^2, y_j^2, \dots, y_i^{l_i}]$
- Random words shuffling after concatenation

Our experiments have shown that MixUp with simple concatenation achieves the best score.

• Manifold MixUp

We implemented **Manifold MixUp**, which was introduced in [11], with similar differences in target mixing. The key idea of this approach is that we are mixing high-level representations of input data. We can get high-level representations from neural network layers. The authors of the original paper proposed the following algorithm.

1. Select a random layer k from a set of eligible layers in the neural network;
2. process two random data minibatches (x', y') , (x'', y'') as usual, until reaching layer k . After this step we get two minibatches $(f_k(x'), y')$, $(f_k(x''), y'')$ (if we consider that $f_k(x)$ – output of k -th layer in neural network);
3. use **Input MixUp** on these minibatches $(f_k(x'), y')$, $(f_k(x''), y'')$. After third step we get mixed minibatch:

$$f_k(x) = \lambda f_k(x') + (1 - \lambda)f_k(x''), \text{ where } \lambda \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \alpha)$$

$$y = \text{MixUp}(y', y''),$$

where $\text{MixUp}(y', y'')$ – caption mixing in Input MixUp (simple concatenation)

4. continue the forward pass in the network from layer k until the output using the mixed minibatch $(f_k(x), y)$;
5. compute the loss value and gradients.

Our implementation has some differences:

1. Data mixing.

We used Manifold MixUp with a 0.5 probability. We mixed high-level representations only at $k = 3$ layer – encoder output layer and $\alpha = 16$.

2. Caption mixing.

We applied a modified Input MixUp for targets, which was described above.

Augmentations below were implemented by **pysndfx** library [12].

• Reverb

Reverb is a shortened form of the "reverberation". It is a musical effect, which sounds like an echo.

We used Reverb with **reverbance**, **room_scale**, **stereo_depth** parameters from $U[0, 50]$ distribution.

• Pitch

Pitch is a feature of sound note, which represents the concept of how high or how low this note is. We used Pitch augmentation with **shift** parameter from $U[-300, 300]$ distribution.

• Overdrive

It is a type of distortion. This effect is achieved by saturating the values in an amplifier. We used Overdrive augmentation with **gain** parameter from $U[2, 10]$ distribution.

• Speed

This augmentation changes the speed of audio. We used Speed augmentation with **factor** parameter from $U[0.9, 1.1]$ distribution.

Every type of augmentations was applied online with 0.5 probability to each sample.

3.3. Neural networks architectures

In this work we will compare following network architectures:

1. DCASE2020 Baseline [9].

The baseline neural network consists of an encoder and a decoder.

The encoder is a three-layered bidirectional [13] GRU [14] with tanh activation function and a residual connection [15] between the second and the third layer. All but the last layer have 128 cells and the last one 256. This results correspondingly to 256 and 512 total cells due in bidirectionality (2×128 and 2×256).

The decoder is a one-layered GRU with tanh activation functions, followed by a fully-connected layer with softmax activation functions. The GRU layer consists of 256 cells, it takes as input the last output of the encoder and produces a matrix $Y \in R^{N_{\text{words}} \times K}$, where N_{words} – words amount in vocabulary, K – maximum tokens in prediction.

An illustration of the DCASE2020 Baseline is in Figure 1.

2. Modification v1 DCASE2020 Baseline.

We modified DCASE2020 Baseline network architecture by adding mean aggregation between encoder and decoder.

3. Modification v2 DCASE2020 Baseline

We modified DCASE2020 Baseline network architecture by adding a fully-connected layer between encoder and decoder.

4. Modification v3 DCASE2020 Baseline

We modified DCASE2020 Baseline network architecture by adding an attention mechanism between encoder and decoder [16].

An illustration of the DCASE2020 Modifications v1, v2, v3 are in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

3.4. Training

The neural networks were trained¹ using Adam optimizer with the 0.0004 learning rate and Cross-Entropy loss. Dropout rates were 0.25 and 0.25 for the first and third encoder layers outputs; the batch size was 40. The neural networks were trained before Cross-Entropy loss or SPIDer metric convergence on holdout set (20% of Clotho development data split) with reducing learning rate on plateau scheduler with patience = 8. The training was performed on GPU NVIDIA RTX 2080 TI. The code was written on PyTorch framework.

3.5. Post-processing

We have noticed that predicted captions have a lot of sequences with repeated tokens. So we decided to compress each sequence with repeating tokens in captions into one element (ex. caption [$\langle SOS \rangle, a, a, a, b, g, g, c, \langle EOS \rangle$] $\xrightarrow{\text{compress}}$ [$\langle SOS \rangle, a, b, g, c, \langle EOS \rangle$]), but the SPIDer score got worse.

4. EVALUATION

The evaluation was performed on Clotho evaluation test split (20%). We used a lot of metrics – BLEU₁, BLEU₂, BLEU₃, BLEU₄ [17], ROUGE_L [18], METEOR [19], CIDEr [20], SPICE [21], **SPIDer**. **SPIDer** - main metric [22], so we will describe it in details:

¹These training settings are applied unless otherwise specified.

Figure 1: DCASE2020 Baseline and v1, v2 modifications architectures

- **CIDEr** (Consensus-based Image Description Evaluation) – metric, which was introduced in [20]. CIDEr measures the similarity of generated sentence against a set of ground truth sentences written by humans. This metric shows a high agreement with human’s judgments of consensus. Using sentence similarity, the notions of grammaticality, saliency, importance, and accuracy (precision and recall) are inherently captured by the CIDEr metric.
- **SPICE** (Semantic Propositional Image Caption Evaluation) – metric, which was introduced in [21]. SPICE captures human judgments over model-generated captions better than other automatic metrics (CIDEr, METEOR, etc.). Furthermore, SPICE can answer questions such as “Which caption-generator best understands colors?” and “Can caption-generators count?”.
- **SPIDer** - metric, which is an average of CIDEr and SPICE metrics, so it has combined benefits from both metrics:

$$\text{SPIDer} = \frac{\text{CIDEr} + \text{SPICE}}{2} \quad (2)$$

4.1. Description of submitted systems to DCASE2020 CHALLENGE

We will describe five approaches (1-4 were submitted):

1. Ensemble of 4 models, which are described below. We select unique predicted tokens by every model for each audiofile, then concatenate 4 strings of tokens.
2. This approach is based on Modification v2 of DCASE2020 Baseline and MixUp augmentation. It was trained with lr=0.0001.

Figure 2: Modification v3 (attention) DCASE2020 Baseline architecture

3. This approach is based on Modification v2 of DCASE2020 MixUp, Reverb, Pitch, Overdrive, Speed augmentations. It was trained with lr= 0.0001.
4. This approach is based on Modification v3 of DCASE2020 Baseline and MixUp augmentation. It was trained with ReduceOnPlateau scheduler with step= 5 and starting lr= 0.0004.
5. This approach is based on Modification v3 of DCASE2020 Baseline and Reverb, Pitch, Overdrive, Speed augmentations. It was trained with ReduceOnPlateau scheduler with step= 5 and starting lr= 0.0001.

4.2. Experiments

In this part we will compare DCASE2020 Baseline with its modifications (v1, v2, v3).

We will also compare DCASE2020 Baseline model and its modifications (v1, v2, v3) with different data augmentations:

1. Input Mixup;
2. Manifold Mixup;
3. Reverb, Pitch, Overdrive, Speed (Another augmentations).

Table 1 presents obtained results.

Augmentations can help achieve better results in most cases, as we can see from the Table 1.

Augment.	Models	Baseline	v1	v2	v3
Without augmentations		0.059	0.060	0.070	0.067
Input MixUp		0.073	0.070	0.078	0.074
Manifold MixUp		0.018	-	0.065	0.077
Another augmentations		0.064	0.064	0.075	0.070
Input MixUp + Another augmentations		0.072	0.064	0.076	0.068
Manifold MixUp + Another augmentations		0.029	-	0.066	0.079

Table 1: Results of experiments. SPIDER metric.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1. Conclusion

In this paper, we made an effort to improve machine understanding of audio in limited training data conditions and without pre-trained models. We showed the impact of augmentations (Input and Manifold MixUp, Reverb, Pitch, Overdrive, Speed) in the audio captioning task. We compared different modifications of DCASE2020 Baseline architecture. The best performance was showed by DCASE2020 Modification v3 (attention) with following augmentations: Manifold MixUp, Reverb, Pitch, Overdrive, Speed. The evaluation of the proposed method was produced with SPIDER metric.

5.2. Future work

Currently, there are no experiments with transformer architectures [23] in papers about the audio captioning task. We suppose that transformer architecture can reach a competitive result. We consider that better word and phrases representations [24] paired with professor forcing RNN training approach [25] may improve the model.

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